

GUARANTEE OF PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT AND A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE

Mirzabekova Feruza Nasriddinovna

Andijan State University Senior Lecturer of the
Department of Human Physiology and Life Safety.

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ABSTRACT

The practical result of physical education in human activity in this scientific article is the degree of perfection of a person's physical fitness and knowledge and skills of movement, high vitality, achievements in the field of sports, mental development. In the formation of the National gene pool, the correct Organization of a healthy lifestyle and the healthy education of the younger generation, physical education and sports are used as a spiritual and ideological tool.

Today we are trying to build a democratic society based on the heritage of ancestors, national values, based on the requirements of our own way of life. It is the healthy human factor that underlies these actions. The formation of a healthy person through physical education and sports should be the task of an entire society. While each person, family, parent can bring physical education and sports to the level of habit, the respect of society as a value leads to the continuous practice of physical education and sports.

Large-scale work is being carried out to form a healthy lifestyle in our society, create conditions in accordance with the requirements of the time for the regular practice of physical education and mass sports of the population, especially the younger generation, build confidence in their will, strength and capabilities in youth through sports competitions, develop courage and patriotism, develop feelings of loyalty to

It is especially noteworthy that representatives of our country achieve high results at the Olympic Games, World Championships, Asian Games and championships, as well as international competitions, the prestige and sports potential of Uzbekistan is growing in the world, magnificent sports facilities are being built in the regions of our republic in accordance with world standards, sports games "sprouts of Hope", "perfect generation"

At the same time, in all regions of our country, there are important and urgent tasks to promote and promote the important importance of mass sports in the life of a person and family, the basis of its physical and spiritual health, to protect young people coming to life from harmful habits, to create conditions for them to realize their abilities and talents, to.¹

¹ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг Қарори, 03.06.2017 йилдаги ПҚ-3031-сон.

<https://lex.uz/docs/3226019>

In order to further develop physical culture and mass sports in the regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, to attract all segments of the population, especially young people, to regularly engage in physical education and sports, to increase the efficiency of effective use of the conditions created in this regard in our country:

- further improvement of legislation aimed at the development of the system of organization and management of the physical education and sports sphere;
- strengthening the material and technical base of the field of physical education and sports, construction of modern sports complexes, equipping them with modern sports equipment and equipment, development of the private sector in this area;
- scientific and methodological support of institutions of training, retraining and professional development in the field of physical education and sports, and provision of sports schools with highly qualified coaches and medical personnel;
- students and students of educational institutions, Organization of Health, Physical Education, mass sports among the broad segments of the population, holding complex sports competitions, qualifying talented athletes from among young people and their targeted training;
- actively using the capabilities of the media, the Internet network, promoting a healthy lifestyle among the population, conducting extensive information and explanatory work on the content of the program and the process of its implementation.

The physical activity of women of different ages is mainly aimed at two goals, one of which is to improve health, while ikkin-chisi stands side by side with men in the field of Sports, showing their potential and defending their glory. It is known that the number of women engaged in physical education and sports is growing every year. This situation is associated with the development of sports in our republic every day and with the changes that occur in our way of living. The working capacity of the female organism is slightly lower than the working capacity of the male organism, which is due to the anatomical and physiological characteristics of the female organism. Therefore, it is advisable to set the volume of physical loads and exercises that are given to women so that they achieve high results in sports.

When determining the volume of physical work, women are obliged to be given with a deep knowledge of the structure and functional characteristics of the body, otherwise their health will deteriorate, leading to serious injuries, even disability. It is known that every woman goes through the duty of motherhood, it is necessary that the next generation be healthy, energetic, not forgetting that it depends, above all, on the health of the mother. For this, it is necessary that every professional, every coach, who conducts women's sports, is well versed in the physical capabilities of the body.

The reason why the physical working abilities of the female organism are lower than the physical working capacity of the male organism is due to the anatomophysiological characteristics of the female organism. As a result of comparing these characteristics, we encounter the following differences.

1. Women will have an average height of 165 cm and Men 175 cm.
2. The chest is short in women, the diaphragm is located much higher, in men the chest is wide.
3. Women have short limbs and men have relatively long limbs.

4. In women, the length of the spine is longer than in men, especially the waist and neck parts, the girdle between the vertebrae is wide, and the intervertebral discs are thick. The ligaments that connect the vertebrae are much more elastic, ensuring that the body is flexible.
5. In women, the shoulder width is small compared to men, and the pelvis width is large. In general, the female skeleton becomes thinner, lighter, more elastic and mobile.
6. Due to the fact that muscle tissue weighs an average of 30-35% in women and 40-45% in men, women have less muscle strength than men.
7. Adipose tissue is 28-30% in women and 18-20% in men.
8. In the central nervous system, there is also a sexual discrepancy, and the rate of movement reactions is lower in women than in men.
9. Although the female organism has a high level of excitement and sensitivity, but the functionality of physical work is low.
10. 65 ml of blood corresponds to 1 kg of body weight of the female body, and the weight of the heart is 200-250 grams, in men 75 ml of blood per 1 kg of body weight, and the weight of the heart is 250-350 grams. Also the number of erythrocytes is greater in men.
11. The surface of the AL'veoli is 100 m² in women and 150-200 m² in men. That is why men have a much higher lung capacity for Vitality.
12. Since adipose tissue in women is 28-30%, heat generation is higher than in men. But 60% of the heat is more mobilized for the work of organs, 40% for muscle work, and in men, on the contrary, for muscle work.

In some types of sports, women show better results than men. This is manifested in the High combination of anatomical and physiological indicators of the female body, willpower and flexibility when performing exercises that require qualities. Even though they have relatively little muscle strength, when performing physical exercises, they are able to skillfully distribute muscle tension evenly over a large number of muscle groups. For this reason, the movement of women is expressed much more subtle, flat, gentle, clear and beautiful. The structure and functional characteristics of the organism of women do not give the opportunity to ba-jar work that is performed with high strength, or requires a high degree of endurance. In the case of men, for example, the low content of Erie-trocytes, hemoglobin, oxygen capacity in the blood, the small size of the heart, the low capacity of the lung vitality and the minute volume of the breath limit the possibility of doing their long-term work. This suggests that the aerobic capacity of the female body is less than that of men. The difference between the physical ability of women and men is also manifested in the change in the function of the respiratory and circulatory systems when performing work of the same volume. The maximum absorption of oxygen in women is 25-30% less than in men and is at the highest level at the age of 20-30 years.

As a result of the regular practice of women in sports, positive changes occur in the structure and function of their organism. The correct application of physical exercises, the correct setting of the volume of training, strength and endurance improve the harmony of movement. In the composition of the body, adipose tissue decreases, muscles and ligaments develop, the capacity of the lungs for Vitality increases, the breathing rate decreases, the heart rate slows down, energy consumption decreases, the body's resistance to various diseases increases, the working capacity improves, the figure becomes beautiful, during pregnancy it

feels better, it becomes easy to give birth to a child. In the occurrence of positive changes in the body of women, it is necessary to note that their practice of gymnastic exercises is of particular importance. Especially at the present time, the widespread use of rhythmic gymnastics will be evidence of this opinion.

Subject to strict adherence to the physiological tastes of sports exercises, it will be necessary to take into account the characteristics of each athlete woman. Women's periodic practice of physical exercises they form muscle work, joint mobility and strengthening in their body. This process of improvement of the movement apparatus is observed in the development of physical qualities such as strength, speed, agility, endurance, improves the function and increases the working capacity of organs. It plays an important role in maintaining health.

Simple methods of physical activity in the formation of a healthy lifestyle in the neighborhoods.

The methods of physical recovery of the body are diverse, and each person, based on his own capabilities and aspirations, should choose the types that are convenient for him and regularly engage in it. When practicing physical exercise, it is essential to follow the following.

- 1) among the requirements for physical wellness methods, they are selected by each person according to their age, performance, health and condition;
- 2) performing step-by-step exercises, from simple to complex;
- 3) ensure that all systems in the body, muscles are involved muttanosib;
- 4) doing the exercises regularly;
- 5) avoid strain on certain systems and body parts;
- 6) perform the exercises as outdoors as possible.

A type widely used among physical wellness methods in terms of comfort and popularity is morning hygienic Gymnastics exercises.

In the process of performing and performing the exercises daily in the morning according to the prescribed regimen, it is necessary to control deep and correct breathing. To do this, it is necessary to alternate the room air. The composition of the complex of morning Gymnastics exercises must necessarily include the following exercises:

- Exercises related to body traction;
- Walking (standing in place and moving) exercises;
- Exercises for the muscles of the neck, shoulders and arms;
- Exercises for the body and abdominal muscles;
- Leg muscles (sitting and jumping);
- Exercises for the legs, arms and other groups of muscles (forward, backward, lateral flexion, vibration, etc.);
- Exercises that force you to work in tension;
- Exercises that relax, etc.

To increase the effectiveness of morning Gymnastics exercises: dumbbells, a gymnastic stick, a jumping rope, a ball, etc. are used. It is considered a normative state that the duration of classes does not exceed 15-20 minutes, the heart rate is 90-100 in adults every minute, and 100-110 in children. Hygienic Gymnastics, which is carried out in the morning hours, is the best way to get from sleep to wakefulness, to a state of trigger and to get into active labor, as

well as to have a surge of strength. When choosing morning gymnastics classes, everyone should take into account their origin, age from the state of Health.

So if you take up to 10-30 minutes to do morning gymnastics every day, you will have the enthusiasm and vivacity you need throughout the day, increasing the body's chances of fighting various diseases.

In conclusion, the health of each person is in his own hands, strengthening it through morning Gymnastics.

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